

Carbon-13 NMR Signals of Some Phenothiazine Derivatives

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Carbon-13 nmr signal assignments of the CNS depressants promethazine (1), trimeprazine (2), chlorpromazine (3), prochlorperazine (4), triflupromazine (5), isothiopendyl (6) and some of their salts are reported. C-H coupling constant (1J and 2J) measurements have also been made.

THE carbon-13 nmr spectral studies of various synthetic and natural therapeutic agents are of current interest¹⁻³. We report here the carbon-13 nmr spectral assignments of the drugs promethazine [10-(2-dimethylaminopropyl)phenothiazine] (1), trimeprazine [10-(3-dimethylamino-2-methylpropyl)phenothiazine] (2), chlorpromazine [2-chloro-10-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)phenothiazine] (3), prochlorperazine {2-chloro-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)propyl]phenothiazine} (4), triflupromazine [10-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-2-trifluoromethylphenothiazine] (5) and isothiopendyl [10-(2-dimethylaminopropyl)-1-azaphenothiazine] (6) and some of their salts. These compounds are well known for their tranquillizing activity⁴ and their ¹³C nmr spectral studies are of biological as well as of theoretical interest. The assignment of the resonances in the spectra of 1-6 and some of their salts were made by considering the chemical shift theory^{5,6} and is presented in Table 1.

Promethazine (1) displayed four signals at δ 115.5, 122.3, 126.9 and 127.3 for the eight unsubstituted aromatic carbons. A comparison of the resonance positions of the various carbons of thiophenol and 4,4'-dinitrodiphenylsulphide with those of benzene⁶ and nitrobenzene⁶, respectively indicated that the thioether function in the former compounds had little effect on the chemical shifts of the aromatic carbons. Thus it is quite likely that C-1

(as well as C-9) in 1 should be associated with the signal at δ 115.5 and consequently C-3 (and C-7) with the resonance at δ 122.3. The resonances at δ 126.9 and 127.3 should thus be related to C-2 (and C-8) and C-4 (and C-6). Similarly the substituted aromatic carbon signals at δ 125.6 and 145.3 in 1 should be assigned to C-4a (and C-5a) and C-9a (and C-10a), respectively. Trimeprazine (2) also exhibited similar resonances for aromatic carbons as those in 1. The effect of incorporation of a chlorine atom or a trifluoromethyl group at C-2 position in the phenothiazine nucleus as in chlorpromazine (3) and prochlorperazine (4) or in triflupromazine (5) on the chemical shifts of the different carbons in ring A was according to the shift theory^{5,6}. In addition to the resonances at δ 115.6, 122.8, 127.0 and 127.3 for C-9, C-7, C-8 and C-6, three more unsubstituted aromatic carbon resonances at δ 117.6, 134.1 and 144.7 were present in the spectra of isothiopendyl (6). These signals should be readily related to C-3, C-4 and C-2, respectively. Of the four substituted aromatic carbon resonances at δ 117.7, 122.1, 142.8 and 155.2 exhibited by 6, the last one must be associated with C-10a and consequently the signal δ 142.8 was linked with C-9a. The C-5a should be associated with the signal at δ 122.1 from the similarity of the resonance position of C-5a in related compounds 1-5. Thus C-4a was assigned the δ 117.6 resonance.

The resonances for the side chain carbons in 1 were readily accounted for from the splitting pattern in the SFORD spectrum and chemical shift theory. The shift of the $-N(CH_3)_2$ group from C-2' position to C-3' position should cause high field movement of C-1' resonance. Thus C-1' in 3 was related to the signal at δ 45.2. The signal for C-1', C-2' and C-3' in 2 appeared at low field positions compared to the resonance positions for these carbons in 3 due to the deshielding effect of the methyl group at C-2' in 2. C-2'' and C-6'' in 4 was linked to δ 52.8 resonance since it experienced more shielding γ -effect than C-3'' and C-5'' (δ 54.7).

In the spectra of the salts of 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6 small deshielding of aromatic carbons were observed, the substituted aromatic carbons being

- 1 $R^1 = H, R^2 = CH_3, R^3 = N(CH_3)_2$
- 2 $R^1 = H, R^2 = CH_3, R^3 = CH_2N(CH_3)_2$
- 3 $R^1 = Cl, R^2 = H, R^3 = CH_2N(CH_3)_2$
- 4 $R^1 = Cl, R^2 = H, R^3 = CH_2-N(CH_2)_4-N-OH$
- 5 $R^1 = CF_3, R^2 = H, R^3 = CH_2N(CH_3)_2$

TABLE I—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) AND COUPLING CONSTANTS (Hz) OF THE PHENOTHIAZINE DRUGS I-6 AND THEIR SALTS

Carbon	Promethazine (1) ^a Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$	Trimeprazine(2) ^b Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$	Chlorpromazine (3) ^a Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$	Prochlorperazine (4) Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$	Triflupromazine (5) ^a Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$	Isothiopendyl (6) ^a Shift $^1J(\text{OH})$, $^2J(\text{OH})$
1	115.5 (117.3)	115.8 (117.4)	115.6 (116.8)	115.4	111.6 (112.8)	144.7 (145.6)
2	126.9 ^c (128.6) ^d	126.9 ^c (128.3) ^d	126.9 ^c (128.3) ^d	132.7	118.5 (118.2)	178.7, 7.4 (180.1)
3	123.3 (124.4)	122.2 (123.9)	122.2 (123.3)	122.4 ^c	118.7 (119.7)	165.0, 8.7 (168.5)
4	127.3 ^c (129.1) ^d	127.3 ^c (128.8) ^d	127.3 ^c (129.1)	137.4	137.3 (138.4)	162.9, 6.7 (168.0, 7.7)
4a	125.6 (126.4)	125.7 (126.2)	125.6 (126.2)	123.0	139.8 (140.7)	117.6 (119.3)
5a	125.6 (126.4)	125.7 (126.2)	125.6 (126.2)	124.2	123.9 (124.2)	122.1 (122.2)
6	127.3 ^c (129.1) ^f	127.3 ^c (128.8) ^f	127.1 (128.5) ^d	127.0	127.4 ^c (129.2) ^d	137.3 ^c (139.4) ^d
7	122.3 (124.4)	122.2 (123.9)	121.9 ^c (124.2)	121.7 ^c	122.9 (124.3)	162.9, 6.8 (162.1)
8	126.9 ^c (128.6) ^f	126.9 ^c (128.3) ^f	127.1 (128.6) ^d	127.0	127.3 ^c (128.2) ^d	162.5, 6.6 (160.4)
9	115.5 (117.3)	115.8 (117.4)	115.6 (117.4)	115.4	115.7 (117.5)	159.0, 7.2 (157.6)
9a	145.3 (145.0)	145.5 (145.8)	144.1 (144.2)	144.0	144.1 (143.8)	142.8 (142.8)
10a	145.3 (145.0)	145.5 (145.8)	146.2 (147.0)	146.0	145.4 (146.2)	155.2 (154.3)
1'	50.5 (47.8)	52.0 (51.2) ^g	45.3 (44.6)	44.9	45.2 (44.5)	46.4 (47.2)
2'	55.7 (59.4)	38.6 (27.7)	24.6 (22.4)	33.8	24.5 (22.4)	56.2 (61.3)
3'	12.1 (12.7)	125.1, 3.8 (26.6) ^g	56.5 (55.7)	54.9	56.6 (55.7)	12.2 (12.2)
N-OH, or N(OH) ₂ , O'-OH ₂	40.7 (40.4)	133.1, 4.9 and 45.8 (44.0)	45.1 (43.4)	45.6	45.0 (43.4)	40.6 (40.3)
2'' 6'' 3'' 5''		16.8 (16.1)				139.0 (139.8)
				52.8		132.2 (143.9)
			54.7	131.1		126.9, 3.5 (128.9)
						133.5, 4.9 and 4.8 (144.0)

a. Values for the hydrochloride salt are given in the parentheses.
 b. Values for the tartrate salt are given in the parentheses; CH(OH) δ 74.7, COOH δ 173.9.
 c,d,e,f. Values along the vertical column are interchangeable.
 g. In the coupled spectra the signals were very weak.

relatively less influenced. C-2' in 1 and 6 salts were deshielded appreciably but some side chain carbons experienced small shielding effects in the corresponding salts.

Experimental

The carbon-13 nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian Associates CFT-20 NMR spectrometer operating at 20.1 MHz in the FT mode. The compounds were submitted to PND, SFORD and noise coupling with nO_2 to establish the carbon shifts, degree of protonation and J values. The samples were run in 10 mm o.d. tubes using $CDCl_3$ as solvent as well as internal lock and internal standard. The spectra of the salts were taken in D_2O serving as solvent and internal lock while dioxan was used as internal standard. All solutions were ca 10-15% in concentration. The chemical shifts reported are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS ; $\delta_{TMS} = \delta_{CDCl_3} + 76.9 \text{ ppm} = \delta_{Dioxan} + 67.4 \text{ ppm}$. The spectra were run with sweepwidth 4000 Hz, pulsewidth 10 μs (approximately 45° tilt angle) and about 2 s delay in between pulses.

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References

1. S. P. SINGH, S. S. PARMAR, S. A. FARNUM and V. I. STENBERG, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1978, **15**, 1083 and references therein.
2. A. PATRA, A. K. MUKHOPADHYAY and A. K. MITRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1245.
3. A. PATRA, A. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, A. K. MITRA and A. K. ACHARYYA, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1981, **15**, 99.
4. P. G. STECHER, (Ed.), "The Merck Index", Merck & Co., N. J., 1968.
5. J. B. STOTHERS, "Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1972, p. 197.
6. G. C. LEVY and G. L. NELSON, "Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy for Organic Chemists", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 81.